

CONSERVATION OF BIODIVERSITY IN OUR COUNTRY AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. In the article, the effective and rational use of natural resources, preservation of resources for the future generation, correct explanation to the young generation that resources are inexhaustible, the unique, unique, valuable natural objects and complexes in our republic, preserving the genetic fund of plants and animals, preventing the negative impact of human activities on nature, the main factors of human impact on biodiversity are the growing consumption of biological resources, human production activities, agriculture, and the expansion of human settlements and so on.

Key words: natural resources, land, water, landscapes, vegetation cover, global climate changes, biological diversity, biosphere, ecological systems.

Аннотация. Мақоллада tabiiy resurslardan samarali, oqilona foydalanish, kelajak avlod uchun resurslarni asrab-avaylash, resurslar bitmas-tuganmas ekanligini o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodga to'g'ri tushuntirish, respublikamizdagi o'ziga xos, noyob, qimmatli tabiiy obyektlarni va majmualarni, o'simliklarning va hayvonlarning irsiy fondini saqlab qolish, inson faoliyatining tabiatga bo'lgan salbiy ta'sirini oldini olish, bioxilma-xillikka odamlar ta'sirining bosh omillari biologik resurslar iste'molining o'sib borayotganligi, insonning ishlab chiqarish faoliyati, qishloq xo'jaligi hamda odamlar yashaydigan joylar kengayib borayotganligi va hokazolar to'g'risida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tabiiy resurslar, yer, suv, landshaftlar, o'simliklar qoplami, global iqlim o'zgarishlari, biologik xilma-xillik, biosfera, ekologik tizimlar.

I. INTRODUCTION

Development of the country's economy, efficient and rational use of natural resources, preservation of resources for the future generation, correct explanation to the young generation that resources are inexhaustible, providing them with erological education and training, environmental protection it is desirable to create resource-saving technologies in the development of the country's economy, to preserve land, water, plant resources, as well as biodiversity, to use natural resources - gas, oil, coal, etc. rationally.

Today, global climate change is one of the global problems faced by the entire world community. One of the main causes of global climate changes is the increase in anthropogenic influence on nature and the increase in anomalous events and pressure. The negative changes occurring on the earth as a result of global climate changes have covered many countries. Desertification and desertification processes are rapidly developing as a result of climate change, especially in areas with scarce water resources and severe fresh water problems. The adoption of the strategy of sustainable development in Uzbekistan until 2030, the mutual coordination of economic, social and ecological components, which are considered as means of achieving sustainable development, in ensuring the socio-economic development strategy of our republic, improving the lifestyle of the country's population, increasing the well-being of the people, and their ensuring proportionality is a difficult task. Economic and ecological components are closely

related to each other and lead to the formation of new ideas about the need to assess the external impact of people on the environment.

II. MAIN PART

In the concept of sustainable development, it is said that "Nature is not an inheritance from ancestors, but a wealth borrowed from generations". The goal of the idea of sustainable development is to ensure the integrated ecological, economic and social development of the modern human society, taking into account the needs of future generations.

It is known that the document adopted by the heads of state and government in the period up to 2030 at the summit of the United Nations General Assembly on Sustainable Development held in September 2015 is a new global obligation in principle. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals and associated targets cover a wide range of issues, from health and well-being to climate change, from gender equality to changes in consumption and production patterns.

Today, in our republic, it is necessary to preserve unique, unique, valuable natural objects and complexes, the genetic fund of plants and animals, to prevent the negative impact of human activity on nature, as well as to study natural processes, the natural environment comprehensive measures to create a system of protected natural areas for the purpose of monitoring, improving environmental education and upbringing are being implemented consistently.

New types of protected natural areas — preservation and restoration of landscapes, flora and fauna, including rare and endangered species included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan, other natural objects and complexes, as well as improvement of the ecological environment, state biosphere reserves, complex, landscape, custom reserves were created, which help to ensure rational use of natural resources. At the same time, the fact that protected natural areas are under the control of several agencies does not provide an opportunity to ensure their effective management and implement a unified state policy in this area. In order to increase the effectiveness of the system of state management of protected natural areas, their further development, as well as to preserve the biodiversity of the republic's ecosystem:

Under the authority of the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Committee of Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Committee of Forestry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Chotkal Biosphere Reserve, Zomin, Surkhan, Nurota and Kyzylkum State Reserves, as well as the Lower Amudarya State Biosphere Reserve have been launched. In the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the following 5 protected natural areas are under state protection, including the "Southern Ustyurt" state reserve; "Beltov", "Okpetki" and "Okdarya-Kazakhdarya between two rivers" state reserve reserves; On the basis of the "Sudochye" state reservation reserve, there are "Sudochye lakes system" state reservation reserves.

Biological resources are natural plant and animal resources of the earth, micro-organisms, as well as the collection of small insects and creatures. Biological resources include plant resources, as well as cultivated and wild plants that occur in nature. Their species are extremely diverse, plant resources grow and develop during the vegetation period, produce seeds at the end of the vegetative period, and end after living their life as an animal world. All kinds of living organisms - plants, animals, fungi and bacteria, microorganisms that provide a full life of people are biological resources for humans, that is, natural bioresources.

The complex of plant organisms distributed in regions, districts, and certain areas of all scales is called flora, and the complex of animal organisms is called fauna. The flora and fauna of a given area make up a whole biota.

Picture №1. Biodiversity is a unique manifestation of diversity.

Biodiversity protection is an important issue, and according to the norms of international law, biodiversity protection, development of the system of protected natural areas, their management and preservation, and ensuring their effective functioning are considered one of the urgent tasks. In 1992, the Convention on Biological Diversity was adopted by the United Nations, and it entered into force as an international document a year later. Biodiversity is important for the future, and biodiversity is not a static concept, it recognizes that all biological parts of nature are interdependent and interdependent. Often, three levels of this concept are distinguished: biological diversity of species - diversity of all plants and animals, including various bacteria and microorganisms; genetic diversity - diversity of genetic material in species and biodiversity among them; diversity of ecological systems - the richness of ecological systems - for example, consists of mountain forests, deserts or savannas, deserts and seas and oceans. These three levels together constitute biodiversity. Therefore, conservation of each of these levels is important for the conservation of biodiversity as a whole.

III. DISCUSSION

Biodiversity can be looked at differently. For example, we can say that we live in the "biosphere", that is, the living part of our planet. The biosphere is a very active substance, but due to the richness of its various biological components, it is very stable in terms of sustaining life. The biosphere is able to withstand external influences and stimuli only due to the richness of biological life. Biodiversity is an important source of economic, aesthetic, health care and cultural well-being of the people in our country. But the decline of biodiversity all over the world - the disappearance of unique genes, species and ecological systems - threatens our country as well. The only reason is these people. Humans have created conditions in which more species have become extinct than in all of history since the time of the dinosaurs 65 million years ago.

If the current rate of biodiversity loss continues, half of the species on our planet will disappear in less than 100 years as a result of human actions to destroy natural habitats, pollution, and climate change. For example, over the past 40 years, fishing has increased from 20 million tons to 135 million tons per year. 75% of fish stocks have disappeared. Despite this, fish is included

in the diet of every fifth person living on Earth. The main factors of human impact on biodiversity are the growing consumption of biological resources, human production, agriculture, and the expansion of human settlements. About 40 percent of the plant species included in the "Red Book" are disappearing from the composition of the flora directly due to the chaotic and excessive grazing of livestock.

IV. CONCLUSION

The fact that the population's need for natural resources is increasing and their use is not properly implemented is also happening. The foci of the crisis of vegetation due to the influence of livestock are 3-4 km from the settlements. radius areas and water sources - clearly visible in the pastures around the wells. In these places, fodder species are replaced by weeds that are not typical for natural pastures - frankincense, kakra, eshakmia, wormwood, wormwood, etc. It is known that water supply for livestock in pastures far from wells remains one of the main problems in the desert regions of Uzbekistan. Grazing pressure or impact decreases with distance from water sources and causes changes in vegetation cover. In conclusion, rational use of natural plant resources is an urgent task in the conditions of increasing human pressure on pastures. If the relevant requirements and regulations are not followed, it is a bitter truth that these natural resources will become irreversible in the near future.

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